

Dendrochronological analysis of a panel painting, Fastens strid med Fastelavn, KMS1639.

by

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The painting, Fastens strid med Fastelavn, ascribed to Pieter Bruegel the elder (1526/30(?)-1569), is painted on a single oak panel (fig. 1). A dendrochronological analysis of the panel was carried out, to discover the date and provenance of the tree used in its manufacture. This report describes the results of this analysis.

Fig. 1. Fastens strid med Fastelavn, KMS1639, Oil on oak panel, 25 x 34 cm (photo Aoife Daly).

Dendrochronological analysis of painted panels is conventionally carried out by paring at the end-grain of the wood to gain an uninterrupted view of the tree-rings, to enable measurement of their thickness. However, a method developed by me over the last four years, where non-invasive dendrochronological analysis of historical wooden artworks is carried out, by taking the tree-ring measurements from the longitudinal section of the timber (Daly & Streeton 2017) has been successfully attempted in this analysis.

The back and ends of the panel has been treated with a varnish or glue. It was therefore not possible to analyse the tree-rings in cross-section at the end-grain at the sides of the painting. However, the longitudinal section, on the back surface (fig. 2) was sufficiently clear of glue, to justify an attempt at taking the measurements from this surface.

The surface was photographed with a macro lens (fig. 3), with a ruler for scale, for subsequent measurement on computer monitor. Three photo series of the back were taken, and two of these were used for attaining measurements. The two measurement series agree very well, except at the outermost c. 15 rings, where the glue obscured the wood anatomy.

Fig. 2. Fastens strid med Fastelavn, KMS1639, the back of the panel (photo Aoife Daly).

Fig. 3. Fastens strid med Fastelavn, KMS1639, macro photograph of the longitudinal section of the wood, at the back of the panel (photo Aoife Daly).

Where reliable tree-ring measurements could be achieved, a tree-ring curve of 145 years in length has been derived. Approximately 16 more heartwood rings partially obscured by glue are preserved in the panel. Sapwood is preserved on one corner also (top right on the photograph in fig. 2). The dating position for the tree-ring curve is AD 1384-1528. Accounting for the 16 unmeasured tree-rings and for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree used to make the panel can be placed at c. AD 1553-67 (depicted with green shading in fig. 4). The tree for the panel was felled within the lifetime of Pieter Bruegel the elder, who died in 1569 (marked with blue in fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Fastens strid med Fastelavn, KMS1639. The chronological position of the wood used to make the panel (illustration Aoife Daly).

Provenance

The correlation between the tree-ring curve from the panel and a range of tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe is shown in table 1. The curve achieves high correlation with a range of tree-ring datasets for Northern Poland, and with many of the so-called Baltic chronologies.

As many of the Baltic tree-ring chronologies are built from oak that was exported to Western Europe, it has not as yet been possible to say where, precisely, that these trees grew in the extensive Southern Baltic region. It is possible to distinguish between different groups of the Southern Baltic timber, (named Baltic 1, Baltic 2 and Baltic 3 (Hillam & Tyers 1995)) and these groups most probably represent forests in different areas within the region.

Filenames	-	-	Z2180018x	
-	start	dates	AD 1384	
-	dates	end	AD 1528	
OM040005	AD 1257	AD 1615	7.49	Baltic 2 40 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
0628002M	AD 1225	AD 1445	5.67	Poland Torun Joh. K. (Wazny pers comm)
0952910S	AD 1343	AD 1569	5.60	St.Katharinen (Wazny pers comm)
H11EOM01	AD 1260	AD 1495	5.55	Bordesholmer Altar 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
Z105M002	AD 1297	AD 1479	5.10	Berg tabernacle Norway 1&4 2 timbers (Daly 2014)
Z099103a	AD 1328	AD 1478	4.70	Portrait of 27 year old man master of the 1540s (Daly 2013)
OM040004	AD 1156	AD 1597	4.65	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
Z060001a	AD 1374	AD 1544	4.52	Bruegel Moneylenders Copenhagen (Daly & Läänelaid 2012)
BAL3_IT_AD	AD 1307	AD 1633	4.40	Baltic 3 67 timbers (Tyers & Daly unpubl)
...				
00751M01	AD 1113	AD 1463	4.35	Vejdyb ship 14 trees (Daly 1997)

Table 1. Fastens strid med Fastelavn, KMS1639. Result of the correlation between the oak curve for the panel and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Methodology

Measuring was carried out from the macro images using the program Able Image Analyser, and for the analysis and the calculation of the *t*-value ("t-test"), the programs "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. An extensive network of master and site chronologies for Northern Europe were consulted to find the dating for the tree-ring curve. To estimate the felling date of the oak, a sapwood average for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)) is used here.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Panel											
Z2180018x	Fastens strid med Fastelavn KMS1639 QUSP	145	AD 1384	AD 1528	G	0	N	T	H16 S1	1.66	c. AD 1553-67
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
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